

Towards an understanding of requirements management in software ecosystems

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Abstract

Context: Software ecosystems (SECO) have introduced complexity in requirements management due to multiple actors' collaboration through several organizational boundaries.

Objective: The main contribution of this article is to improve the understanding of requirements management in SECO. We propose a conceptual model whose concepts, definitions, and relationships are grounded in the literature and the modern software industry's practices.

Method: We applied Design Science to build the conceptual model and conducted a Delphi study with 22 experts to assess it. We performed two rounds and adjusted our model according to the experts' judgment.

Results: We reached a conceptual model containing 43 concepts and their relationships that help to understand requirements management in SECO. Moreover, we provided a glossary with a definition of each concept. This conceptual model can help abstract the complexity of the requirements management in SECO, improving their understanding.

Conclusions: By organizing the knowledge of requirements management in SECO, this conceptual model makes it possible to expand the body of knowledge in the area and serves as a basis for new solutions to support requirements management in SECO.

Keywords: Software Ecosystems, SECO, Requirements Management, Conceptual Model, Design Science, Delphi Method

1. Introduction

Requirements management has become even more critical in new software development contexts where multiple actors collaborate through several organizational boundaries and use several communication channels to report their needs and expectations [1]. It is a challenge in the software ecosystems (SECO) context [1, 2]. SECO are formed by multiple products derived from a common technological platform based on a central architecture integrating other systems and establishing a network of actors and artifacts [3]. In SECO, requirements for the products and platforms emerge and propagate through multiple actors' collaboration relationships, which introduces complexity to the requirements management [4, 5]. These multi-party actors are often from different organizations and do not share the same goals [6].

In a systematic mapping study (SMS) on requirements engineering (RE) in SECO, Vegendla et al. [7] identified that requirement management is one of the least addressed RE processes in the SECO literature. For Vegendla et al. [7], there is a lack of guidelines for the RE process in SECO, and more research should be performed to understand requirements management in this context. Another recent SMS defined specific characteristics that differentiate requirements management in SECO from that carried out in other software development contexts [8]. However, this SMS also revealed that several open issues remain on requirements management in SECO. To the best of our knowledge, there is a lack of shared understanding of this process in SECO. Hence, the main goal of this work is to improve the understanding of requirements management in SECO by identifying concepts and their relationships. To do so, we propose a conceptual model called SECO-RM (**R**equirements **M**anagement in **S**oftware **E**COsystems).

To build SECO-RM, we performed an SMS on requirements management in SECO [8] and a field study on open innovation (OI) practices to support requirements management in SECO [9]. Moreover, we consider the SECO meta-model proposed by Wouters et al. [10] to identify SECO concepts and relationships. We evaluated SECO-RM through the Delphi study, which is an experts' judgment technique [11]. As a result, SECO-RM provides a comprehensive view of requirements management through 43 concepts and their relationships.

As the contribution of this work, SECO-RM comprises concepts associated with requirements management in SECO, their definitions, and relationships grounded in the literature and the software industry's practices.

It can also support researchers and practitioners in further developing solutions that support the requirements flows in SECO, for instance. According to Chazette et al. [12], a conceptual model helps abstract, understand, and communicate information regarding a given domain.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the background; Section 3 details the research method; Section 4 presents SECO-RM; Section 5 details the evaluation of SECO-RM; Section 6 depicts our main findings, perspectives for using, and implications; Section 7 discusses the threats to the validity; and, finally, Section 8 concludes this work.

2. Background

SECO have become an active topic of research in software engineering (SE) and are an integral part of modern software development [13]. Manikas [3] classified SECO into three types: (i) proprietary (PSECO) - SECO based on proprietary contributions, typically protected by intellectual property; (ii) open source (OSSECO) - SECO based on contributions which are typically open to the rest of the actors; or (iii) hybrid - SECO that supports both proprietary and open source contributions. SECO have offered organizations advantages related to innovation dynamics and collaboration networks. However, the dynamic set of actors introduces challenges to requirements management in SECO [14].

Requirements management provides visibility for the development process of the software, which is a guarantee for the success of the software [15]. It establishes a baseline for the project management and aims to: (i) organize the identified requirements; (ii) control the requirements change; (iii) maintain requirements traceability; and (iv) manage the artifacts containing information regarding requirements [15]. Requirements management is considered challenging in the context of SECO due to the complexity of ecosystem dependencies, which make understanding and alignment between actors difficult [1].

According to Jansen [16], opening requirements management to external actors is challenging because it is necessary to keep requirements transparent between a keystone and external actors. External actors are contributors that provide indirect value to the ecosystem [16]. Managing several requirements in SECO also brings challenges to the partnerships between a keystone and external developers [1]. For Linåker et al. [2], there may be conflicting agendas and a lack of control over these several requirements due to multiple

actors in SECO, resulting in the misalignment of internal RE processes such as requirements management.

Several conceptual models for RE applied to different software development contexts have been proposed in the literature to improve understanding of RE in these contexts. A conceptual model is an abstract representation of a system designed to assist its understanding, outlining the main entities, their attributes, relationships, and interactions [17]. As related work, Qureshi et al. [18] proposed a conceptual model to address the communication and coordination challenges during requirements change management in global software development. Popoola et al. [19] proposed a conceptual model that integrates advancements and innovations in requirements elicitation. Finally, Chaipunyathat et al. [20] proposed a conceptual model of RE in cloud project delivery. However, none of them focused on requirements management in SECO.

3. Research Method

To build SECO-RM, we used Design Science [21], a method that guides the design, evaluation, and refinement of software artifacts and has been commonly adopted in SE and information systems research areas. Figure 1 shows the three main steps of our research method.

Figure 1: Our research method.

3.1. Step 1: Problem Investigation

In this step, we identified and understood the problem to be investigated [21]. To do so, we conducted an SMS [8] and performed a field study [9].

We also analyzed the SECO meta-model proposed by Wouters et al. [10] to support identifying SECO concepts and relationships. We detail each of these sub-steps next.

3.1.1. Step 1.1: Conducting SMS

We performed an SMS to gather evidence and explore the state of the art of requirements management in SECO [8]. We defined three research questions (RQ) to characterize requirements management in SECO:

- RQ1: What are the characteristics of requirements management in SECO context?
- RQ2: What are the approaches used to support requirements management in SECO context?
- RQ3: How have the existing approaches to requirements management in SECO context been assessed?

As a result, we selected 29 studies¹ and answered those three RQ. We defined nine characteristics of requirements management in SECO (RQ1). These characteristics include opening organizational boundaries, power relations between multi-party actors, open communication channels, and emergent requirements spread across multiple requirements artifacts stored in different repositories. We also identified four types of approaches to support requirements management in SECO: tool, method, model, and practice (RQ2). Finally, we found that only three out of ten selected studies that propose approaches to requirements management in SECO present some form of assessment (RQ3). Our results showed that requirements management in SECO involves multi-party actors, tends to be an open process, and can benefit from OI practices due to the inherent openness of ecosystems. We used these main results to build SECO-RM. More details about this SMS are available at Malcher et al. [8].

3.1.2. Step 1.2: Conducting Field Study

A main result of the SMS refers to the fact that requirements management in SECO can benefit from the OI paradigm. SECO imply a shift from

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8131745>

closed organizations and processes towards more open structures where external actors become increasingly involved in the development [1]. Hence, we performed a field study based on interviews with 21 professionals involved in requirements management in SECO to identify OI practices in this context [9]. To do so, we defined the RQ:

- RQ1: How do OI practices influence requirements management in SECO?

As a result, we identified 10 OI practices used to support requirements management in SECO and 14 communication channels used to receive/provide requirements from/to external actors. The communication channels identified were categorized into open online, closed online, and face-to-face communication channels. Our main results showed that the use of multiple open communication channels by internal and external actors allows different OI practices, such as crowdsourcing, co-creation, collaboration, coopetition, and customer immersion, which provides knowledge sharing across the ecosystem and affects requirements management. More details about this field study are available at Malcher et al. [9].

3.1.3. Step 1.3: Analyzing SECO Meta-model

Wouters et al. [10] proposed a comprehensive meta-model describing possible entities and relationships that constitute a SECO to create a common language for academic researchers for SECO. We used this meta-model due to its comprehensiveness and because it is the only one found for SECO. The meta-model consists of five themes: “*actors and roles*”, “*products and platforms*”, “*boundaries*”, “*ecosystem health*”, and “*strategy*”. Only the themes “*actors and roles*” and “*products and platforms*” of the SECO meta-model were related to the results of our SMS [8] and field study [9]. Therefore, we only considered these themes when building SECO-RM.

Regarding the theme *actors and roles*, Wouters et al. [10] identified 46 entities. For our model, we considered the entities *actor*, *relationship*, *role*, *hub*, *niche player*, and *keystone* as the concepts related to requirements management in SECO. The concepts *hub* and *niche player* are role main categories that grouped several other roles in SECO [10].

Regarding the theme *products and platforms*, Wouters et al. [10] identified 27 entities. For our model, we consider the entities *product* and *platform* as concepts related to requirements management in SECO. The other entities

were these two main entities' specializations, aggregations, or compositions. Therefore, they can be conceptually represented by these entities.

Once the problem is known, the next step aims to use the studies performed to find, select, and define the concepts associated with requirements management in SECO as well as design the conceptual model.

3.2. Step 2: SECO-RM Design

This step consisted of specifying a solution to solve the problem [21]. We based this step on the theory-building framework proposed by Sjøberg et al. [22], which possess the sub-steps: (i) Step 2.1: Defining constructs (elements involved in a theory); (ii) Step 2.2: Defining propositions (relationships among constructs); (iii) Step 2.3: Providing explanation (which provides the context and evidence for propositions); and (iv) Step 2.4: Determining scope (in which the theory is valid).

In **Step 2.1**, we examined the entire text of the 29 primary studies selected in our SMS to identify constructs, i.e., concepts associated with requirements management in SECO. After defining possible constructs, we analyzed the field study to verify the correspondence of concepts and finally checked the work of Wouters et al. [10] to confirm SECO concepts. For example, we identified the *keystone* concept in the selected studies in the SMS. Next, we analyzed whether any field study interviewees had expressed it and checked whether the meta-model of Wouters et al. [10] presented this concept. We reproduced this same process to other concepts. In some cases, there was no direct correspondence between the three studies, and what prevailed was the evidence identified in the literature. In the end, we identified a set of 57 concepts that we believed were constructs related to requirements management in SECO. The results of this step are presented in Section 4.

In **Step 2.2**, we described the SECO-RM propositions that are the relationships among their concepts [22]. Propositions can explain phenomena through the association among concepts and indicate how these concepts interact with each other [22] and are the essence of conceptual models [23]. SECO-RM propositions describe a given fragment of the conceptual model and emerge from evidence extracted from primary studies of our SMS. We used propositions to better represent SECO-RM.

In **Step 2.3**, we provide evidence-based explanations from the literature for each of the SECO-RM propositions. For instance, for proposition 2, we provided the following explanation: “*There are product, integration, and platform requirements in SECO [24]. The most demands in a SECO are*

integration requirements involving data types exchanged and data dictionary [25]. The RE process in SECO should have three main focuses: the product, the platform, and the ecosystem (holistic view to identify integrations between products) [5]". Hence, the selected primary studies in our SMS are the key elements in such explanations. We presented the explanations for each proposition in Section 4.

In **Step 2.4**, we determined the conceptual model scope when supposing that SECO-RM is suitable for three types of SECO (PSECO, OSSECO, and hybrid) since the studies we conducted did not focus on a specific type of SECO.

3.3. Step 3: SECO-RM Evaluation

This step evaluated whether the implemented solution to solve the problem (in our case, SECO-RM) meets the expected objectives [21]. We applied the Delphi method [11] to evaluate the SECO-RM. The Delphi method uses an iterative process to reach an expert consensus to make decisions, evaluate, or conduct predictive research [26]. It involves collecting and analyzing data anonymously, as well as consulting several experts who can review their answers in different rounds until they reach a consensus [27]. Delphi studies contribute to evaluating RQ and allow for the validation of propositions in scenarios that are not yet mature by leveraging experts' judgment [28, 29]. In our study, we applied the Delphi method to evaluate the SECO-RM, considering the steps presented by Olivero et al. [29], as described next.

3.3.1. Step 3.1: Planning Evaluation

This step can be divided into the following activities: selecting subject, selecting experts, and statistical processing [29].

Selecting Subject. A proper selection of the subject and the correct questionnaire design directly impact the quality of the results and the requirements to choose the experts [29]. This activity results in the identification of RQ that define the purpose of the questionnaire and the development of the questionnaire itself. Hence, we defined two RQ that aim to evaluate SECO-RM:

- RQ1: Do the experts agree with the propositions presented for SECO-RM?

- RQ2: Do the experts agree that SECO-RM meets the criteria of ambiguity, explanatory power, parsimony, generality, and utility?

Based on the RQ, we defined the following purpose of the questionnaire: assess experts' agreement regarding the seven propositions of SECO-RM and compliance with the overall evaluation criteria presented by Sjøberg et al. [22]. Ferreira et al. [23] claimed that propositions can be used for evaluation purposes since they represent the entire conceptual model, i.e., the concepts, the association among them, and the diagrammatic representation of SECO-RM. According to Sjøberg et al. [22], the criteria ambiguity, explanatory power, parsimony, generality, and utility are the most relevant for evaluating empirically-based SE theories, as in the case of SECO-RM.

Regarding the questionnaire development, we divided it into three parts. Part I had five demographic questions to outline the experts' profiles. Part II comprised seven closed questions on the SECO-RM propositions. Additionally, one optional open question for each proposition was available for additional contributions. We presented the SECO-RM propositions in Section 4. Part III had five closed questions related to the overall evaluation criteria of SECO-RM [22] and five optional open questions associated with each closed question to additional comments.

We conducted a pilot to evaluate the questionnaire with three professionals with experience in requirements management and SECO to verify the questionnaire's clarity and effectiveness. The main suggestions obtained from carrying out the pilot were: (i) provide supplementary material with the definition of the areas of knowledge that are asked in Part I of the questionnaire; (ii) improve the quality of the figures; (iii) add a note to explain the element of the conceptual model that represents the existence of other "roles" in SECO; and (iv) make the table that explains the UML representation of the relationships between elements also available in the supplementary material. After carrying out the pilot, we made the necessary adjustments, and the final version of the questionnaire is available in the supplementary material [30].

The questionnaire was available to the panel members using a Google Forms² link. We did not disclose the panel's composition and addressed all communications individually to ensure the anonymity of the study. We

²<https://docs.google.com/forms/>

anonymized the results in each round’s report by eliminating references to panelist identities.

Selecting Experts. The selection of appropriate experts is essential to the success of the Delphi method, as it is directly related to the quality of the results generated [26, 28, 31]. However, selecting the appropriate participants is one of the most important challenges in Delphi studies [28]. There are no clear guidelines in the literature to define criteria to configure the profile of the most suitable participant [28]. Elements such as professional background, knowledge of the subject to be analyzed, and willingness to participate might be valid criteria to be a panel member [31]. Moreover, there is no consensus in the literature regarding the number of participants in a Delphi study [28]. Several works stated that most Delphi studies use a panel ranging from 15 to 20 members [26, 31, 32]. Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [31] recommended that the number of panelists be high enough to be representative and low sufficient to keep the process manageable.

As we aim to evaluate a conceptual model of requirements management in SECO (SECO-RM), the panel should ideally be composed of experts in both fields. However, finding people who are experts in both areas at the same time is not such an easy task. The community of researchers in SECO is not as large as in other more mature areas of SE [13, 33]. This fact makes it difficult to find specialists who ideally fit this profile. For this reason, we followed the strategy used by Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [31] that designed a panel composed of experts in one of the fields involved in the evaluation with at least some theoretical knowledge about the other.

We invite the experts between active members of the SECO and RE communities, members of the program committee, and organizers of SECO and RE-related conferences such as the International Workshop on Software Engineering for Systems-of-Systems and Software Ecosystems (SESoS)³ and International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE Conference)⁴. We used convenience sampling based on being nearby as well as the availability of the experts [34]. Initially, we invited 50 experts to participate in this study, receiving a positive answer from 22 of them, who forwarded us answers during the different rounds of the method. Table 1 and 2 present the expert panel’s experience in requirements management and SECO. According to

³<http://www.sesos-wdes.icmc.usp.br/>

⁴<https://requirements-engineering.org/>

Alarabiat and Ramos [28], requesting the expert’s experience self-rating may be a suitable technique to identify participants with adequate expertise in the problem area of a Delphi study.

Table 1: Experience type of panel members.

Type of experience	Requirements management		Software ecosystems	
	Number of experts	%	Number of experts	%
Practical	21	95.45%	18	81.81%
Theoretical	1	4.55%	4	18.19%
No knowledge/No experience	0	0%	0	0%

Table 2: Experience level of panel members.

Degree of experience	Requirements management		Software ecosystems	
	Number of experts	%	Number of experts	%
Very high	10	45.45%	7	31.82%
High	8	36.37%	8	36.37%
Average	3	13.63%	3	13.63%
Low	1	4.55%	2	9.09%
Very low	0	0%	2	9.09%

Table 1 shows that all panel members possess theoretical experience in requirements management and SECO, with most having practical knowledge (95.45% and 81.81%, respectively). In turn, Table 2 presents a simple sum of the number of experts that marked their experience level in knowledge areas directly associated with SECO-RM (i.e., requirements management and SECO). For instance, considering the requirements management experience level, 10 participants informed that their level experience is *Very high*, eight informed *High* experience, and so on. The sum of each column related to the number of experts is 22, corresponding to the total of participants. In a broader view, we observe that most participants had *very high* or *high* experience in requirements management or SECO.

Table 3 summarizes the experts’ work sectors. We identified that there is a balance between specialists who work exclusively in academia, exclusively in industry, and in both. Table 4 presents the academic degrees of the experts, revealing that 50% hold M.Sc. degrees, while the other 50% have Ph.D. We also highlight the geographical distribution of the panel, with experts coming from five different countries: Brazil, Canada, Germany, Netherlands, and Nicaragua. This geographical distribution provides different local interpretations of our conceptual model, bringing varied points of view to the panel. Hence, we believe that the expert panel of our Delphi study comprises a

well-balanced group of people with suitable knowledge of two fields (requirements management and SECO), including practitioners with practical and theoretical experience.

Table 3: Type of work sector of the experts.

Type of work sector	Number of experts	%
Academy	8	36.36%
Industry	7	31.82%
Both academy and industry	7	31.82%

Table 4: Academic degree of the experts.

Academic degree	Number of experts	%
M.Sc.	11	50.0%
Ph.D	11	50.0%

Statistical Processing. The statistical processing in Delphi studies includes defining the statistical approaches to analyze the experts’ responses in each Delphi round and defining the stopping conditions that determine when it is no longer necessary to launch additional rounds [29]. Therefore, defining the statistical process before conducting the Delphi study prevents authors’ bias in determining the results [29].

Analysis of experts’ responses in each Delphi round aims to determine whether they have reached a consensus and identify response stability between successive rounds [29]. The consensus and the stability can be measured using several statistical approaches in Delphi studies [35, 36]. In our Delphi study, we applied descriptive analysis to analyze the consensus, Cronbach alpha [37] to measure the reliability of the questionnaire, and Kendall’s W [38] to measure the stability of the responses among rounds.

Descriptive analysis measures data frequency distribution and central tendency [39]. We used the Likert scale 5-point and 3-point to measure the Delphi questionnaire with values converted to numeric values. Hence, we calculated the median, mode, standard deviation (SD), interquartile range (IQR), and percentage of agreement and disagreement for each proposition or question related to the overall evaluation criteria. These values are often used as the basis of consensus assessment in Delphi studies [40]. In our Delphi study, such values helped us identify the experts’ panel consensus and their agreement on each of the propositions and overall evaluation criteria.

IQR is often used to measure consensus in Delphi literature due to its robustness as a statistical measure [27, 41]. IQR represents the distance

between the 25th and 75th percentile values in opinions, with a smaller IQR indicating a larger consensus [40]. The median better measures the degree of panel support for each proposition or overall evaluation criteria. If it is high, we can conclude that the panel has a high level of agreement [40]. In turn, SD allows us to observe the dispersion of results, which is directly related to the IQR. An SD value of less than 1.5 indicates that the experts have reached a consensus [40].

Cronbach alpha measures a particular test’s reliability level [42]. Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [31] explained that several works use the Cronbach alpha to determine the reliability of a questionnaire that includes Likert questions type. Its values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating better internal consistency among the questionnaire items [42]. Table 5 presents the interpretation recommendations for Cronbach’s alpha values proposed by George and Mallery [43]. Other Delphi studies used this recommendation [29, 31].

Table 5: Cronbach’s alpha interpretation recommendations of George and Mallery [43].

Range	Meaning
> 0.9	Excellent
0.81 – 0.9	Good
0.71 – 0.8	Acceptable
0.61 – 0.7	Questionable
0.5 – 0.6	Poor
< 0.5	Unacceptable

Kendall’s’ W is a statistical algorithm that measures the agreement among several raters assessing a set of items [38]. The closer Kendall’s’ W to 1, the more similar the order of the sets of items is [38]. A high value of Kendalls’ W can mean that experts apply the same standards when assessing the items [38]. We used Kendall’s W to calculate stability between two consecutive Delphi rounds. We calculate Kendall’s W for each item and then compute the general Kendall’s W by averaging Kendall’s W values for all items. Finally, we analyze the result to determine the level of stability between the rounds. According to Gisev et al. [44], the interpretation of Kendall’s W is often subjective. Table 6 shows the interpretation of Kendalls’ W used by Gisev et al. [44] in the context of Delphi studies.

Stopping conditions in Delphi studies can be reached by consensus, stability level, or when enough rounds have been conducted [29]. We defined the consensus based on IQR and SD as the stopping condition in our Delphi study, as in other Delphi studies [26, 27]. Therefore, we will consider that consensus has been reached in a round if the $IQR \leq 1$ and $SD \leq 1.5$.

Table 6: Kendalls' W interpretation recommendations of Gisev et al. [44].

Range	Meaning
> 0.8	Almost perfect stability
0.61 – 0.8	Substantial stability
0.41 – 0.6	Moderate stability
0.2 – 0.4	Fair stability
< 0.2	Poor stability

Furthermore, stability between Delphi rounds must be at least moderate according to the interpretation presented in Table 6. We also defined criteria for assessing the agreement or disagreement of experts for each proposition or overall evaluation criterion of the conceptual model according to the strategy of Olivero et al. [29]. This strategy defines that the experts agree with the propositions or overall evaluation criteria if more than 51% of experts gave it a score of 4 or 5.

3.3.2. Step 3.2: Conducting and Reporting Evaluation

This step comprises the following activities: first round, generating statistical data, and further rounds [29].

First Round. It aims to introduce the questionnaire to the experts. According to Olivero et al. [29], there are two approaches to conducting the first round in Delphi studies: use a well-structured questionnaire or use a preliminary version for a test round. We chose the first alternative because we previously carried out a pilot with three practitioners with experience in requirements management in SECO, who helped us structure and review the questionnaire.

Generating Statistical Data. It analyzes and interprets experts' responses through previously defined statistical processing. Delphi study organizers produce an anonymous summary of the experts' panel opinion to determine if the Delphi method has reached a stopping condition [29].

Further Rounds. It occurs as long as the Delphi study does not reach its stopping condition. In each new round, Delphi study organizers send the experts the previous round summary containing statistical data with the expert's comments for each question in the study [29]. Based on this summary, the experts analyze the panel's general results and can modify or confirm their previous answers. Two or three rounds usually suffice to reach a consensus on the expert panel's opinion [29, 31].

3.3.3. Step 3.3: Determining Results and Conclusions

Once the stopping condition is met, a report is produced containing an analysis of the gathered information, and a Delphi study is finished.

4. SECO-RM Conceptual Model

This section introduces the first version of SECO-RM, composed of a diagrammatic representation, a glossary, and a set of propositions. Figure 2 presents SECO-RM in their representation through a UML class diagram with 57 concepts associated with requirements management in SECO and the relationships among them. Table 7 details the seven SECO-RM propositions (P1 to P7). The glossary that describes the 57 concepts related to requirements management in SECO is presented in the supplementary material [30] due to space limitations in the article.

Table 7: SECO-RM propositions.

ID	Proposition	Explanation
P1	Multiple <u>actors</u> that may have one or more <u>roles</u> in <u>software ecosystems</u> , considering the type of software ecosystem, the <u>products</u> developed, and the <u>platform's</u> evolution, participate in <u>requirements management</u> , and influence other actors through power relations	SECO are based on the collaboration of multiple actors [3]. Each actor can have one or more roles in a SECO [10]. These roles are grouped into two principal categories: hubs and niche players [10]. The multiple actors in a SECO are susceptible to power relations influencing requirements management activities [4]. However, the power relations are different in OSSECO and PSECO [45].
P2	<u>Requirements management</u> in <u>software ecosystems</u> is based on a <u>process</u> that manages <u>platform</u> , <u>products</u> , and <u>integration requirements</u>	There are product, integration, and platform requirements in SECO [24]. The most demands in a SECO are integration requirements involving data types exchanged and data dictionary [25]. The RE process in SECO should have three main focuses: the product, the platform, and the ecosystem (holistic view to identify integrations between products) [5].
P3	The <u>requirements management process</u> in <u>software ecosystems</u> has specific <u>characteristics</u> related to <u>actor relationships</u> , <u>artifacts</u> , <u>concepts/definitions</u> , and <u>activities</u> that differentiate it from traditional software development.	Characteristics can be considered process elements [46] and categorized as actors' relationships, artifacts, concepts/definitions or activities [46] of the requirements management in SECO. The requirements management process in SECO has specific multi-party actors' relationships from different organizations [4], requirements defined in several artifacts distributed in the ecosystem [47], concepts/definitions related to their openness [1], informality [4], collaboration [25], and decentralized [2] and activities related to requirements identification, change management, communication, negotiation, prioritization, and traceability, which tend to differ from traditional software development [7].

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Table 7 – Continued from previous page

ID	Proposition	Explanation
P4	The <i>requirements management process</i> in <i>software ecosystems</i> uses different support <i>approaches</i> such as <i>methods</i> , <i>models</i> , <i>practices</i> , and <i>tools</i> .	Approaches can be considered as the types of contributions of the published studies in SE [48, 49, 50]. The requirements management in SECO has been performed with the support of tools [51, 52, 5], models [53, 47], methods [54]; and practices [16].
P5	The <i>requirements management process</i> in <i>software ecosystems</i> manages <i>requirements</i> that are not stored in a central <i>repository</i> but spread across different types of requirements <i>artifacts</i> , each with its own repository.	The requirements sharing in SECO must be expanded to multiple external actors [55], so there is often no central repository with requirements defined [52, 2]. Decentralized repositories (i.e., issue trackers, mailing lists, and source code repositories) store the requirements in SECO [47].
P6	The <i>requirements management process</i> in <i>software ecosystems</i> manages <i>requirements</i> communicated in <i>strategic</i> and <i>emergent requirements flows</i> through several <i>communication channels</i> such as <i>open online</i> , <i>closed online</i> , and <i>face-to-face communication channels</i> .	Requirements are largely introduced in SECO via two general information flows [56, 4]. The strategic requirements flow considers business goals and global strategies, while the emergent requirements flow results from local just-in-time RE activities and the open communication paradigm [56, 4]. Multi-party actors who are not responsible for the requirements but contribute to discussing them beyond organizational boundaries originate emergent requirements [53]. These requirements are communicated using multiple channels: online open, online closed, and face-to-face [51].
P7	<i>Requirements management</i> in <i>software ecosystems</i> uses <i>open innovation practices</i> .	Requirements management in SECO is cross-domain and uses the OI paradigm [57]. OI positively and negatively impacts requirements management in SECO [58]. RE needs to consider the implicit changes in OI and adapt to this new context [59].

5. SECO-RM Evaluation and Refinement

The SECO-RM evaluation occurred through a Delphi study with 22 experts in requirements management and/or SECO providing their opinions. We carried out two rounds to reach a consensus among the experts. The study began in December 2023 (first round) and ended in April 2024 (second round). The study questions were measured using 3-point and 5-point Likert scales, later converted to numeric values to produce a statistical study of the results (Table 8). Moreover, we defined two keywords to describe and summarize the decision of the expert panel, as the strategy of Olivero et al. [29]: agreement and disagreement. We measured the agreement by calculating the percentage of experts who chose “I strongly agree”, “I agree”, or “Yes” to each proposition. Similarly, we measured the disagreement through the percentage of experts who chose “I disagree”, “I strongly disagree” or “No”. The following subsections describe the Delphi method execution round by round.

Table 8: Likert scale interpretation.

5-points Likert scale	3-points Likert scales	Numeric value
I strongly agree	Yes	5
I agree	-	4
I neither agree nor disagree	Sometimes	3
I disagree	-	2
I strongly disagree	No	1

5.1. First Round

The first round of the Delphi study started in December 2023 and finished in February 2024. The experts evaluated the seven SECO-RM propositions and answered five questions related to the five criteria presented by Sjøberg et al. [22] for the overall evaluation of the model. We then carried out descriptive analyses of the responses related to the propositions and evaluation criteria, analyzed the reliability of the questionnaire, and presented conclusions for the round, as detailed next.

Descriptive Analysis of Propositions. Table 9 presents the expert panel’s evaluation results for the SECO-RM propositions in the first round. It includes the median, mode, SD, IQR, and percentage of agreement and disagreement for each proposition.

Table 9: First-round results for SECO-RM propositions

Proposition	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement		% Disagreement	
					Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
P1	4.5	5	0.67	1	50%	40.91%	0%	0%
P2	4	5	0.83	1	45.45%	40.91%	4.55%	0%
P3	5	5	1.02	1	54.55%	22.73%	9.09%	0%
P4	4	5	0.85	1.75	45.45%	27.27%	0%	0%
P5	4	4	1.06	0.75	27.27%	54.55%	9.09%	4.55%
P6	4	4	0.59	1	45.45%	50%	0%	0%
P7	4	5	1.22	2	31.82%	22.73%	13.64%	4.55%

In the first round, experts did not express strong disagreement with the SECO-RM propositions, except P5 and P7, receiving higher levels of disagreement. In addition, the experts’ agreement on propositions seems to be high. Figure 3 presents the percentages of agreement and disagreement of the expert’s panel about the SECO-RM propositions. We also highlight that the median and mode values were greater than 4 for all propositions, which means that “I agree” and “I strongly agree” were the options mostly selected by the experts.

Figure 3: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on SECO-RM propositions in the first round.

To identify the necessary adjustments to be made to SECO-RM, we conducted a qualitative analysis of the expert’s responses to the open questions on propositions. We initially performed an open coding [60] to identify excerpts in these answers and create codes. Next, we used axial coding described by Charmaz [60] to group the codes into categories. The first author conducted the open and axial coding processes, and the other authors reviewed the codes and categories to ensure the reliability of the results. We organized the answers to the open questions, codes, and categories into a supplementary document [30] to track the results in several iterative cycles with discussions between the authors, always supported by the literature. Table 10 presents examples of the coding process.

As a result, we identified 30 codes related to the seven SECO-RM propositions. We categorized them according to the actions to be taken: R (Reinforcement of the proposition), NC (No changes in SECO-RM), and Chg (Changes in SECO-RM). Eight codes reinforced the propositions (Table 11), eight did not require adjustments in the conceptual model as they would

Table 10: Illustration of the coding process.

Excerpt on Proposition 1: “Multiple actors... participate in requirements management and ***may*** influence other actors through power relations”	
Code	Category
C1 - Multi-party actors can influence the requirements management and other actors in SECO.	Changes in SECO-RM (C)
Excerpt on Proposition 2: “Regarding integration requirements, I would like to be sure that it covers the process elements of a digital ecosystem (which do not only concern [technical] integration but money flow, asset flow, contract negotiation etc.)”	
Code	Category
NC5 - Integration requirements must cover digital ecosystems.	No changes in SECO-RM (NC)
Excerpt on Proposition 3: “The requirements management process in software ecosystems does indeed exhibit specific characteristics that differentiate it from traditional software development”	

mischaracterize the propositions or were related to statements that conflict with the literature (Table 12), and 14 codes associated with adjustments to be made in the conceptual model (Table 13). We made simple adjustments to some propositions (P1, P2, P5, P6) and significant adjustments to others (P3, P4, P7). We deeply analyzed each change to improve the conceptual model.

Table 11: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that reinforce (R) propositions in the first round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Reference
P1	R1	Influence is a type of power explored in SECO, which may be different according to the type of SECO.	[4, 25, 45, 61]
	R2	An actor can have one or more roles and influence other actors in a SECO.	[10]
P2	R3	There are product, platform and integration requirements in SECO.	[24]
P3	R4	SECO require approaches considering its specific characteristics and problems, such as those related to requirements management.	[3, 62]
P4	R5	Requirements management in SECO uses several approaches to deal with the SECO complexity.	[16]
P5	R6	Requirements are usually spread out over several requirements artifacts in SECO (each of them with its own repository).	[4, 2]
P6	R7	Multiple communication channels allow multi-party actors to share requirements in the SECO.	[63]
P7	R8	Requirements management in SECO can benefit from OI practices due to the inherent openness of SECO.	[1, 52, 64]

Table 12: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that do not change (NCh) the conceptual model in the first round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Justification
P1	NCh1	Categorization of actor’s roles in SECO is incomplete.	An entity “...” represents the other roles in SECO. Additionally, a note associated with this entity explains it.
	NCh2	Keystone controls product in SECO.	Keystone is the role an actor takes when controlling the platform. In SECO, external actors can control products that are around the platform [10].
	NCh3	There must be a relationship between the concepts of actor and role.	An actor is associated with a role in SECO through the concept “Relationship” [10].
P2	NCh4	Integration requirements must cover digital ecosystems.	SECO-RM is limited to improving the understanding of requirements management in SECO.
	NCh5	It is necessary to include other types of requirements.	Product, integration, and platform requirements are the overall categories of requirements usually defined in SECO. [5, 24].
P3	NCh6	Requirements management in SECO is not different from that carried out in other software development contexts.	Requirements management in SECO has specific characteristics that differentiate it from other software development contexts [4, 2, 7].
P4	NCh7	It is necessary to include metrics/measures as requirements management approaches in SECO.	In SE, approaches usually refer to the methods, models, practices, and tools developed to support the software development processes [48, 49, 50].
P7	NCh8	Requirements management does not use OI.	Several works investigated OI in the requirements management context, including in SECO [9, 65, 66].

Table 13: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that change (Ch) the conceptual model in the first round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Action
P1	Ch1	Multi-party actors may influence the requirements management and other actors in SECO.	Add “may” in P1 and adjust the multiplicity.
	Ch2	Other social, technical, and business relations may influence requirements management in SECO.	Adjust P1 so that it is more comprehensive using only the term “influence”.
P2	Ch3	The definition of platform requirements is not clear.	Add the definition of platform requirements in the evidence for P2.
	Ch4	The definition of product requirements is not clear.	Add the definition of product requirements in the evidence for P2.
	Ch5	Actors must explicitly participate in requirements management in SECO.	Add the participation of multi-party actors in P3.
P3	Ch6	Requirements management in other software development contexts also can be collaborative and decentralized.	Present evidence of the characteristics that differentiate requirements management in SECO from that carried out in other software development contexts.

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Table 13 – Continued from previous page.

Proposition	ID	Code	Action
	Ch7	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “actor relationships”, “artifacts”, “concepts/definitions”, and “activities”.	Better specify the concepts related to the characteristics of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from that carried out in other software development contexts.
	Ch8	The relationship between requirements management in SECO and other RE activities is not detailed.	Clarify that a characteristic of requirements management in SECO is that its practices overlap with other cross-project RE activities in the ecosystem.
	Ch9	Requirements management in SECO can be centralized, depending on the type of SECO.	Remove the decentralized concept from P3.
P4	Ch10	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “methods”, “models”, “practices” and “tools”.	Detail the specificity of the methods, models, practices, and tools that support requirements management in SECO in P4.
P5	Ch11	There may be SECO with only one central requirements repository.	Add “may” in P5.
P6	Ch12	The use of multiple communication channels also occurs in other software development contexts.	Present more evidence about strategic and emergent requirements flows and highlight the role of multiple communication channels in SECO.
	Ch13	The communication channel concept is not clear.	Add communication channel definitions and examples in the evidence for P6.
P7	Ch14	Requirements management in SECO does not always use OI.	Modify the term “uses” to “benefits”.

Descriptive Analysis of Overall Evaluation of SECO-RM. Table 14 presents the expert panel’s evaluation results for the questions regarding the overall evaluation of SECO-RM in the first round.

Table 14: First-round results for SECO-RM overall evaluation criteria [22].

Criteria	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement	% Disagreement
C1	5	5	1.7	2	59.09%	22.73%
C2	5	5	1	0	86.36%	4.55%
C3	5	5	1.26	0	81.82%	9.09%
C4	5	5	1.18	2	63.64%	4.55%
C5	5	5	1.45	0	77.27%	13.64%

In the first round, experts also did not express strong disagreement about the achievement of overall evaluation criteria by the SECO-RM. The experts’ agreement appears to be high about the evaluation criteria. The median and mode value was 5 for all criteria, which means that “Yes” was the option selected by the experts the most. Only C1 (related to the utility) and C5 (related to the ambiguity) received higher levels of disagreement compared

to others. Figure 4 presents the expert panel’s agreement and disagreement percentages.

Figure 4: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on overall evaluation criteria in the first round.

To identify the necessary adjustments to SECO-RM, we also conducted a qualitative analysis of the expert’s responses to the open questions on overall evaluation criteria. As a result, we identified seven new codes, two related to no changes in SECO-RM (Table 15) and five related to changes in SECO-RM (Table 16). Moreover, we also identified codes previously related to the model’s propositions (Ch7, Ch8, Ch14).

Table 15: Codes associated with comments on overall evaluation criteria that do not change the conceptual model in the first round.

Criteria	ID	Code	Justification
C1	NC9	Organize concepts related to characteristics at the same level.	The concepts were already organized at the same level.
C2	NC10	Tool is not an approach.	In SE, approaches usually refer to the methods, models, practices, and tools developed to support the software development processes [48, 49, 50].

Table 16: Codes associated with comments on overall evaluation criteria that change the conceptual model in the first round.

Criteria	ID	Code	Action
C1, C2, C4	Ch15	The definition of keystone is not clear.	Add the definition of keystone in the evidence for Proposition 1.
C2, C3	Ch16	The definition of hub is not clear.	Add the definition of hub in the evidence for Proposition 1.
C1	Ch17	There are OI practices that are not directly related to requirements management in SECO.	Group more specific OI practices (e.g., hackathon and venturing) into more generic practices (e.g., collaboration, co-creation, and co-competition) to simplify the model.
C4	Ch18	The definition of scenarios in the Delphi questionnaire is not clear.	Change the question related to C4 in the Delphi questionnaire, adding scenario definition in the research context (different types of SECO).
C5	Ch19	The use of the model is not clear.	Change the question related to C5 in the Delphi questionnaire, adding explicitly the model purpose.

Reliability Analysis. We calculated Cronbach’s alpha for the reliability analysis using the “psy” package⁵ of R⁶. The value obtained was 0.7. According to George and Mallery [43], this Cronbach’s alpha value obtained indicates questionable reliability of the proposed questionnaire.

Round Conclusions. As conclusions of the descriptive analysis of the propositions and overall evaluation criteria of SECO-RM in the first round, we identified that most experts indicated agreement with the conceptual model. However, two propositions (P4 and P7) and two overall evaluation criteria (C1 and C4) did not reach a consensus among experts. In other words, the stopping condition ($IQR \leq 1$ and $SD \leq 1.5$) defined previously was not reached (see Tables 9 and 14). Hence, considering the experts’ opinions in the first round, we can state that there are still propositions and conceptual model elements to improve and/or clarify. Therefore, we concluded that our research requires a new Delphi round.

5.2. Second Round

The second round of the Delphi study started in March 2024 and finished in April 2024. This round aimed to clarify and refine the results obtained during the first round. To do so, we performed the following actions: (i)

⁵<https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=psy>

⁶<https://www.R-project.org/>

we changed the SECO-RM, considering the experts’ recommendations (see Tables 13 and 16 for details); (ii) we rephrased the SECO-RM propositions, considering the changes performed; (iii) we updated the glossary; and (iv) we modified the Delphi questionnaire. The diagrammatic representation of the version of the SECO-RM after the modifications made based on the results of the first round, the SECO-RM propositions rephrased and updated version of the glossary are available in the supplementary material [30].

To start the second round, we sent the new version of the questionnaire and an anonymous report with aggregated results of the first round and all comments provided by the experts. After reading the report and analyzing the reformulated propositions, experts could maintain or modify their answers from the previous round. Only 19 of 22 experts participated in this round. For experts who did not participate, we kept their first-round evaluation according to the strategy of Torrecilla-Salinas et al. [31].

Descriptive Analysis of Propositions. Table 17 presents the experts’ evaluation results for the SECO-RM propositions in the second round. The experts’ level of disagreement regarding most of the model’s propositions decreased or remained the same as in the first round. The level of disagreement increased in only one proposition (P4). However, the level of disagreement ranged from 0% to 5.56%, which is not a significant increase. Figure 5 shows the percentages of agreement and disagreement of the panel of experts on the model’s propositions in the second round.

Table 17: Second-round results for SECO-RM propositions

Proposition	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement		% Disagreement	
					Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
P1	5	5	0.59	1	63.64%	31.82%	0%	0%
P2	5	5	0.5	1	59.09%	40.91%	0%	0%
P3	4.5	5	0.84	1	50%	36.36%	4.55%	0%
P4	4	4	0.96	1	40.91%	45.45%	0%	5.56%
P5	4	4	1.02	1	31.82%	50.00%	4.55%	4.55%
P6	4	5	0.72	1	45.45%	40.91%	0%	0%
P7	4	4	0.68	0.75	18.18%	54.55%	0%	0%

The initial low disagreement from the first round and the clarifications provided by some other experts’ comments might explain the reduction of disagreement. Moreover, the median and mode values remained above 4 for all propositions in the second round, meaning that “I agree” and “I strongly

Figure 5: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on SECO-RM propositions in the second round.

agree” remained the options most selected by experts. This result implies that the experts are convinced of the other panelists’ arguments.

In the second round, the number of comments from experts decreased. Moreover, several of them were related to codes “reinforce of proposition” or “no changes in SECO-RM” previously defined in the first round as presented in the supplementary material [30]. Hence, we presented in this round only codes related to “changes in SECO-RM” (Table 18).

Table 18: Codes associated with comments on SECO-RM propositions that change (Ch) the conceptual model in the second round.

Proposition	ID	Code	Action
P3	Ch7	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “actor relationships”, “artifacts”, “concepts/definitions”, and “activities”. [first round]	Better specify the concepts related to the characteristics of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from that carried out in other software development contexts.
	Ch8	The relationship between requirements management in SECO and other RE activities is not detailed. [first round]	Clarify that a characteristic of requirements management in SECO is that its practices overlap with other cross-project RE activities in the ecosystem.

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Table 18 – Continued from previous page.

Proposition	ID	Code	Action
P4	Ch10	There are abstract concepts that need to be more specific to requirements management in SECO, such as “methods”, “models”, “practices” and “tools”. [first round]	Better specify the concepts related to the approaches of requirements management in SECO that differentiate it from that carried out in other software development contexts.
P5	Ch23	Heterogeneity and integration between requirements repositories must be explicit.	Explain the heterogeneity and integration between requirements repositories in the evidence for P5.
P6	Ch25	The emergent requirements concept is not clear.	Better specify the concept of emergent requirements in the evidence for P6.

Descriptive Analysis of Overall Evaluation of SECO-RM. Table 19 presents the experts’ evaluation results to the overall evaluation criteria of the model in the second round. The experts’ level of disagreement regarding all overall evaluation criteria decreased or remained the same as in the first round. Figure 6 shows the percentages of agreement and disagreement of the panel of experts to the overall evaluation criteria in the second round. The median and mode values remained equal to 5 for all criteria in the second round, meaning that “Yes” remained the option most selected by experts.

Table 19: Second-round results for SECO-RM overall evaluation criteria [22].

Criteria	Median	Mode	SD	IQR	% Agreement	% Disagreement
C1	5	5	1.1	0	77.27%	4.55%
C2	5	5	0.85	0	95.45%	4.55%
C3	5	5	0.7	0	86.36%	0%
C4	5	5	0.85	0	95.45%	4.55%
C5	5	5	1.45	0	77.27%	13.64%

We did not find comments related to changes in SECO-RM in the open questions on general evaluation criteria. We only found codes that were already identified in the first round, which were related to no changes in SECO-RM and the reinforcement of propositions. The second round coding process is available in the supplementary material [30].

Reliability Analysis. The value obtained for Cronbach’s alpha in the second round was 0.71. Cronbach’s alpha value increased compared to the first round and continues to indicate acceptable reliability of the questionnaire [43].

Stability Analysis. We calculated Kendall’s W for the experts’ responses stability analysis between the first and second rounds using the “psy” package of R. The value obtained was 0.51. According to Gisev et al. [44], the

Figure 6: Percentage of agreement and disagreement of the expert panel on overall evaluation criteria in the second round.

value obtained indicates moderate stability between experts' responses in two Delphi rounds.

Round Conclusions. As a main conclusion of the second round, we can state that the experts' panel solved most of the uncertainties expressed in the first round. In this round, the descriptive analysis of the propositions and overall evaluation criteria of SECO-RM indicated that the experts' panel reached a consensus. In other words, the experts' panel responses achieved the stopping condition ($IQR \leq 1$ and $SD \leq 1.5$) defined in Section 3 (see Tables 17 and 19). Furthermore, the panel of experts agrees with all of the SECO-RM propositions and considers that the conceptual model met the general evaluation criteria proposed by Sjøberg et al. [22]. With consensus and a moderate level of stability reached, we concluded our research involving the Delphi method.

5.3. Final Version of the Conceptual Model

Figure 7 presents the diagrammatic representation of the final version of SECO-RM, containing 43 concepts and their relationships. The figure also highlights (in gray) the changes performed in the model after two evaluation Delphi rounds. The final versions of the propositions and the glossary are available in the supplementary material [30].

Figure 7: Final version of the conceptual model for requirements management in SECO with refinements highlighted in gray after the second round.

6. Discussion

This section depicts our main findings and future perspectives on the use of SECO-RM.

6.1. Main Findings

SECO-RM building process was based on the execution of an SMS [8] and a field study [9], in addition to the analysis of a SECO meta-model [10]. Throughout this process, we gathered important observations and reflections on the requirements management in SECO, which we consolidated as a set of main findings. These findings help the SECO community identify and open new research directions regarding requirements management in SECO. The main findings are:

- *Requirements management in SECO is a challenge:* Knauss et al. [4] claimed that SECO introduces complexity in requirements management, and studies published in recent decades have highlighted several challenges related to requirements management in SECO [4, 1, 51]. In the literature (from our SMS) and in practice (from our field study with practitioners), we identified several reasons why requirements management in SECO is challenging. These reasons are related to: (i) the inherent openness of SECO; (ii) the interaction of multi-party actors across multiple organizational boundaries through multiple communication channels; (iii) the existence of emergent requirements flow; (iv) the relationship between platform, product, and integration requirements; and (v) the storage of requirements in artifacts and repositories that can be spread across an ecosystem. These reasons often refer to specific characteristics of requirements management in SECO, which are also the main findings of this work and are detailed later.
- *The inherent openness of SECO influences requirements management activities:* We noticed that it is necessary to consider the openness inherent to SECO [57] to better understand requirements management in this context. Therefore, requirements managers in SECO must have openness in mind [52], even in PSECO. An open platform is a prerequisite for a vibrant SECO [55]. Axelsson and Skoglund [14] explained that SECO are based on an open environment and have a range of actors from different organizations interacting around an open or semi-open platform. We also identified that several studies indicate that

requirements management in SECO is open and can benefit from OI practices [52, 4, 1]. For example, Linåker and Wnuk [52] proposed a model that considers OI practices in the requirements management process in SECO.

- *Multi-party actors influence requirements management in SECO*: Better understanding the roles that multi-party actors can have in a SECO helps to understand requirements management in this context. According to Wouters et al. [10], SECO consists of several actors, which can have one or multiple roles. Valença et al. [67] pointed out that the existence of multi-party actors introduces challenges to requirement management in SECO. Figalíst et al. [6] highlighted that multi-party actors in SECO could not be viewed similarly in large-scale, agile distributed teams because actors in a SECO do not belong to a single organization but to several organizations that share different and possibly competitive relationships (“coopetition”).
- *Requirements management in SECO must consider emergent requirements flow*: Emergent requirements are a reality in SECO and must be managed in this context. They are based on ecosystem trends [4], allow innovation and create a circular flow of requirements knowledge in SECO [1]. Emergent requirements originate from consumers in the ecosystem, who find new ways to use existing services [4]. Moreover, new functionalities offered by external actors can generate emergent requirements [1]. However, it is difficult to map emergent requirements to specific actors, especially since they are generally transversal to several SECO actors [4].
- *Requirements management in SECO must manage product, platform and integration requirements*: The requirements management process at a keystone and its partners within a SECO often overlaps due to several user feedback channels available in the ecosystem. According to Damian et al. [1], two main sources of requirements knowledge exist for a SECO: users of keystone’s core product and the external developers’ products, and external developers, who are users of the platform itself. However, these two sources of requirements knowledge in SECO can often result in a large heterogeneous user base providing product, platform, and integration requirements across multiple channels that need to be managed [5].

- *Multiple repositories can store requirements in SECO*: We noticed that it is necessary to consider multiple requirements repositories in SECO to understand better requirements management in this context. According to Jansen et al. [55], the requirements sharing must be expanded with multi-party actors in SECO. Linåker and Wnuk [52] mentioned that there is often no central repository with requirements defined in SECO. Linåker et al. [47] claimed that decentralized repositories (i.e., issue trackers and source code repositories) store the requirements in SECO. Moreover, several artifacts can represent a requirement, often complementing each other to give a complete picture [2].
- *Requirements communication inside and outside SECO is fundamental*: Requirements management in SECO must monitor multiple communication channels to identify requirements change and emergent requirements. According to Knauss et al. [4], the multiple actors in a SECO often use open online (e.g., app store and forums), closed online (e.g., emails and help desks), and face-to-face (e.g., product demonstrations and technical visits) communication channels. These channels are mainly used to improve and maintain a project’s presence in a SECO and ensure that projects share knowledge at the ecosystem level with multi-party actors with different interests [63].

6.2. Perspectives for Using SECO-RM

Regarding the theoretical contributions, SECO-RM aggregates the long-term knowledge from the literature on requirement management in SECO. It enriches the SECO body of knowledge, providing a unified understanding of concepts and their relationships. Besides the diagrammatic representation of SECO-RM, a glossary of the associated concepts provides a unified and comprehensive description of each concept. Hence, we believe that the SECO community could benefit from this model and adopt it as a starting point for future research on requirements management in SECO.

SECO-RM contributes to the definition of practical strategies for requirements management in SECO and supports the development of tools and methods tailored to the challenges of SECO. It also supports the understanding of the dynamics of requirements management in SECO through: (i) identifying multi-party actors considering their influence in the developing strategies to manage requirements effectively; (ii) integrating OI practices that explore how requirements are sourced, selected, and integrated

from external actors such as user communities and external developers; and (ii) understanding of how requirements emerge and evolve through emergent and strategic requirements flows in the ecosystem, considering ongoing interactions and feedback loops considering.

Regarding the practical contributions, SECO-RM provides a holistic view of requirements management in SECO to professionals, as it comprises concepts, definitions, and relationships. This view supports professionals in their requirements management activities in SECO. For instance, SECO-RM shows that requirements management in SECO should consider the strategic and emergent requirements flows. Another example is that SECO-RM provides an overview of the benefit of practices already used by professionals in SECO requirements management, such as collaboration and cooperation, in the context of OI.

7. Threats to Validity

This section discusses the threats to validity identified in our work, from the SMS execution to the SECO-RM evaluation. We recognize that this process is susceptible to several threats to validity, such as any process that uses a research method. Next, we present these threats according to the classification suggested by Wohlin et al. [68] (construct validity, internal validity, external validity, and reliability) and discuss how we mitigated them.

7.1. Construct Validity

Construct validity refers to the connection between a theory behind an investigation and its observations [68]. It is related to obtaining the correct measures for the concept studied.

To mitigate threats to construct validity in the SECO-RM design, such as the possibility of not identifying some concepts, we performed the following strategy: (i) we reanalyze the open coding process performed in the selected studies from the SMS and in the participant's responses to the field study; and (ii) we carried out several rounds of discussion between the four authors involved in this study until we reached a consensus. This process helped us in the identification of the concepts and relationships among them.

To mitigate threats related to construct validity in the SECO-RM evaluation, such as the inadequate design of the questionnaire, bias in expert selection, and overreliance on expert opinions, we performed a Delphi study

with the following strategy: (i) we carried out a pilot to tune the questionnaire and reduce the ambiguities in the questions; (ii) we carefully selected experts based on their expertise, experience, and relevance to the study topic and ensured a diverse panel of experts representing different perspectives and backgrounds; (iii) we anonymized responses to reduce bias; and (iv) we supplemented expert opinions with empirical data whenever possible.

7.2. Internal Validity

Internal validity refers to uncontrolled factors that may affect the study results [68]. It consists of the results' equivalence with the reality or the degree to which the study minimizes bias.

To mitigate threats to internal validity in the entire process of building SECO-RM, such as the possibility of bias in the execution of the SMS, in the execution of the field study, and in the design and evaluation of our model, we performed the following strategy: (i) we previously defined research protocols with objective criteria related to the selection of studies in our SMS, participants in our field study, and experts in our Delphi study.; (ii) we carried out pilots to ensure the clarity of research instruments; and (iii) we provided references and definitions on requirements management in SECO and detailed instructions in the interviews and during the model evaluation.

7.3. External Validity

External validity refers to the capacity to generalize the results to other contexts, populations, or settings beyond those directly examined in the study [68]. It addresses whether the results obtained in a particular context hold in other situations or with other groups of people.

To mitigate threats to external validity in the entire process of building SECO-RM, such as the existence of non-representative samples of studies and participants in the conducted studies, we performed the following strategy: (i) we employ a hybrid search strategy (search database and snowballing) to identify relevant studies; (ii) we used the convenience sampling to ensure diversity and representativeness in the sample; (iii) we considered the saturation as a criterion for sample size, ensuring that data collection continues until no new themes or insights emerge; and (iv) we carefully documented contextual factors and providing transparent descriptions of procedures carried out.

7.4. Reliability

Reliability refers to the consistency and repeatability of measurements or observations obtained in a study [68]. This aspect concerns the extent to which the data and analysis depend on the specific researchers.

To mitigate threats to reliability in the entire process of building SECO-RM, such as bias in interpreting the explanations extracted from SMS, from the field study, and experts' comments in the model evaluation through the Delphi study, we performed the following strategy: (i) we carried out several cycles of review and discussion of the propositions among the authors of this study; (ii) the first author performed the open coding of data extruded of each study and the other authors reviewed the results; and (iii) we previously defined stopping criteria from analyzing consensus among experts and stability between model evaluation rounds. Conflicts on data analysis results were resolved through discussions among the authors until they reached a consensus.

8. Conclusion

The dynamic nature and inherent openness of SECO introduce complexity to requirements management and make it difficult to understand. The main purpose of this work was to improve the understanding of requirements management in SECO, contributing to the advancement of SECO's body of knowledge. To do so, we proposed SECO-RM, a conceptual model for requirements management in SECO that contains key concepts, their definitions and relationships, and a diagrammatic representation. The SECO-RM build was grounded in an SMS, a field study, and the analysis of a SECO meta-model. After evaluating the SECO-RM through a Delphi study with experts, we obtained a version of the model aligned with the state-of-the-art literature and opinions from industry and academia.

SECO-RM can guide researchers and practitioners in understanding the complexities of requirements management in SECO. Moreover, it can provide deeper insights into the challenges and dynamics of SECO, facilitating the generation of new knowledge and the advancement of theory in this field. By organizing the knowledge of requirements management in SECO, SECO-RM puts together several issues or concerns that must still be researched, including the benefits of OI for requirements management in SECO and the impact of emergent requirements flows in this context.

From the proposition of SECO-RM, we envisioned future work from the perspective of the SECO research community, as in the following: (i) SECO-RM continuous update - SECO-RM must be continuously updated since SECO is still a new area with many research opportunities open. Hence, as new evidence emerges and the body of knowledge on requirements management in SECO expands new concepts and relationships may come to light and could be added to SECO-RM; (ii) SECO-RM validation - It is also necessary to validate the effectiveness of SECO-RM. For this, the conceptual model can be applied in different scenarios, for instance, OSSECO, PSECO and hybrid SECO. The results of such applications could identify improvements in the model; and (iii) SECO-RM as a source of requirements - SECO-RM can be used as a starting point for new solutions, including tools that support requirements management in SECO, considering requirements changes suggested by multi-party actors and their traceability in cross-projects in the ecosystem.

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Data Availability

The authors declare that the data supporting the findings of this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369678>

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